

INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION

Murodov Oybek Torakulovich

"Asia International University"

Assistant teacher of "General technical sciences" department
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686694>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 10-February 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 15- February 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 21- February 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

information technology, education, presentation, multimedia, video.

ABSTRACT

article highlights the advantages of using modern information technologies in classes of general education schools. Information about the role of information technology in conducting modern education is given.

Enter. Today, as Uzbekistan is consistently moving towards building a democratic legal state and a just civil society, fundamental reforms are being implemented in the personnel training system. In the social policy of the state, individual interest and priority of education are decided. The need to provide the educational process with advanced pedagogical and information technologies is one of the conditions of the implementation of the National Personnel Training Program.

As we all know, information is a collection of information about a person, object, evidence, event, event, and process, regardless of the form of presentation. Information technology is the total methods, devices, methods and processes used to collect, store, search, process and distribute information.

The main part. In the educational process, issues of information technologies and their application, innovative changes and approaches, the introduction of any innovation into the system, directly through updating and changing the teacher's activity, are of urgent importance. This activity is continuous work on the basis of news, which is formed and improved over a long period of time. Collection, storage, processing and distribution of information by the teacher contributes to the development of education by introducing innovations into pedagogical activity, has a positive effect on pedagogical activity. In improving the effectiveness of the educational process, information technologies play an important role in independent works such as booklets, informational bulletins, presentations, sample summaries, schemes, graphics and tables. Pupils were given ample opportunities for free creativity and independent work. Presentations prepared on the basis of Internet resources, Power Point, Word computer programs, and programs with informational information are important tools for covering the topic. In such a process, interrelationships between concepts and events are established, personal knowledge of students increases, they actively accept ready-made facts, concepts, and explanations in the situation of independent

solving of problematic issues.

The modern world level of development of information and communication technologies is such that the creation of a national system compatible with the integration of the infrastructures of the world information space and the national information and computing network in the republic is an important factor in the effectiveness of the national economy, management, science and education. These problems are very complex and at the same time urgent for our republic. The results of the implementation of economic, structural and other changes that are currently being carried out depend on how and in what time frame the problems related to informatization are solved in the republic.

The creation of electronic educational tools for educational subjects further expands the possibility of using modern information and communication technologies in teaching these subjects. This, in turn, is the main factor of students' in-depth acquisition of knowledge in these subjects and increases the quality and efficiency of education.

Multimedia is a rapidly developing modern information technology. Its distinguishing features include:

- integrates various types of information: traditional (text, tables, decorations, etc.), original (speech, music, excerpts from video films, TV frames, animation, etc.) in one software product. Such an integration of various devices for recording and displaying information

- education of students and retraining of personnel on the basis of multimedia tools is an urgent issue of today. The concept of multimedia entered our lives in the early 90s. The question is what is he himself? Many experts analyze this term in different ways. In our opinion, multimedia is an embodied form of delivery of educational materials to students based on audio, video text, graphics and animation effects based on software and technical tools of informatics.

Teaching students based on multimedia tools has the following advantages:

- a) there is a possibility of deeper and more perfect assimilation of the given materials;
- b) the passion for close contact with new areas of learning will increase;
- c) as a result of reducing the time of education, achieving the opportunity to save time;
- g) acquired knowledge is kept in one's memory for a long time and it is possible to use it in practice if necessary.

The emergence of the multimedia system has led to revolutionary changes in several professional fields such as education, science, art, computer training, advertising, technology, medicine, mathematics, business, scientific research.

Although the idea of using computers in the educational system appeared much earlier, the use of information technology in all areas of the educational system became more complete after the advent of computers equipped with multimedia devices. was put into practice.

The use of multimedia tools in education provides an opportunity to:

- ensure the humanization of education;
- increase the efficiency of the educational process;
- development of the learner's personal qualities (assimilation, thirst for knowledge, independent education, self-education, self-improvement, creative abilities, ability to apply acquired knowledge in practice , interest in learning, attitude to work);
- development of the learner's communicative and social skills;

- with the help of computer tools and information electronic educational resources, the possibilities of individualization and differentiation of open and distance education will be significantly expanded due to the separate (individual) education of each person;
- to look at the learner as an active learning subject, to recognize his value;
- taking into account the personal experience and individual characteristics of the learner;
- conducting independent educational activities, in which the learner studies and develops independently;
- formation of students' skills in the use of modern educational technologies, which help them to adapt to the current rapidly changing social conditions in order to successfully perform their professional tasks.

According to the possibilities of taking into account the individual characteristics of learners and helping to increase their interest (motivation), as well as according to the qualities of compatibility, interactivity, flexibility of various types of multimedia educational information, multimedia is useful and productive education. lim technology.

Teachers who struggle with computer skills can use simple presentation methods without animation and sound. A presentation may include key concepts and phrases, key words, brochures, diagrams, and visuals on the topic. If the screen for the presentation is set at an angle of 45 degrees, the teacher will be able to attach a presentation on the topic to the students while standing in the center. Visualization and short texts play an important role in the presentation. The process of creating a Power Point presentation is carried out in the following actions: choosing the general decoration of the presentation; choosing the size of the content of the slides (maximum 36 words of 6 lines); add a new slide and its components; selection of slide sizes; use the necessary changes in the decoration of slides; creating sound animation aspects in slide shows.

Videos also play an important role in creating knowledge in the teaching process. Viewing videos autonomously or optional does not give any results. Selected videos should be relevant to the topic and focus on specific goals. The method of using video materials should increase students' interest in the subject and have an emotional impact. When showing videos, the teacher should comment on each video and draw students' attention to a specific goal.

The duration of videos should not exceed 5-7 minutes. According to the theorists of pedagogical technology, it is possible to put the didactic process, that is, technologies into practice, on the basis of clearly defining the didactic issues (didactic purpose, content, and student's mastery) on the topics. Accordingly, the didactic process will consist of the following components:

Motivation. At this stage, the teacher creates the need to learn the subject using different methods.

The following are recommended for such methods:

1. Thematic footage, showing films, showing pictures.
2. Use of statistical materials related to the topic.
3. Working with documents.

These methods encourage students to learn the subject with interest from the very beginning of the lesson. Organization of the student's educational activity on the basis of the

taxonomy of educational goals developed by the American pedagogue scientist B. Bloom will have a positive effect. "Knowing" is the lowest level of the cognitive domain, which means remembering concepts, facts, and principles. At this stage, the student should be able to memorize, remember, name and tell the acquired knowledge.

At the "Understanding" stage, the essence of acquired knowledge is clarified and understood.

At the "Application" stage, the acquired theoretical knowledge and the theoretical aspects of various forms of practical application are mastered (the student knows how to apply the acquired knowledge in practice, but this does not mean that he can apply it).

At the "Analysis" stage, the student has the potential to analyze the acquired knowledge.

At the "synthesis" stage, the student connects the acquired knowledge to each other and can identify common connections.

The "Evaluation" level is considered the highest level, and at this level, the student acquires the skills to express his opinion and evaluate certain concepts, arguments and principles based on the knowledge he has acquired.

The implementation of this process in a sequence creates conditions for the formation of skills and competences in the subject, not only for the student to acquire knowledge. The last component of the didactic process is management of educational activities. In the lesson, the necessary information is transmitted directly from the teacher to the students using communication.

An important aspect of control is that if the learning activity is performed by the student, the control algorithm can be performed by both the teacher and the student.

At the end of the academic subject, it is necessary to control the knowledge of students. The form of control can be as follows: conducting a survey; conducting written work; test taking; creating and solving crossword puzzles; write reviews of scientific articles; writing an abstract.

SummaryBased on the requirements of the present time, in the training of highly qualified personnel, implementation of teaching on the basis of pedagogical and information technologies plays an important role in increasing the quality and efficiency of education. They plan and implement the educational process that guarantees the achievement of the set goals. Provides emotional impact to students through visual materials. After all, 80 percent of the successful course depends on the correct design, organization and implementation of the educational process.

References:

1. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). Zamonaviy ta'limda axborot texnologiyalari va ularni qo'llash usul va vositalari. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 481-486.
2. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.
3. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201.
4. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA YANGI INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 130-139.
5. Turakulovich, M. O. (2023). DEVELOPMENT AND INSTALLATION OF AN AUTOMATIC

- TEMPERATURE CONTROL SYSTEM IN ROOMS. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
6. MURODOV, O. T. (2023). INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
7. Muradov, O. (2024, January). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 46-55).
8. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. Models and methods in modern science, 3(1), 84-93.
9. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(1), 54-63.
10. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 16-27.
11. Bobokulova, M. (2024). IN MEDICINE FROM ECHOPHRAPHY USE. Development and innovations in science, 3(1), 94-103.
12. Bobokulova, M. (2024). INTERPRETATION OF QUANTUM THEORY AND ITS ROLE IN NATURE. Models and methods in modern science, 3(1), 94-109.
13. Bobokulova, M. (2024, January). RADIO WAVE SURGERY. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 56-66).
14. Bobokulova, M. (2024). UNCERTAINTY IN THE HEISENBERG UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 80-96.
15. Bobokulova, M. (2024). BLOOD ROTATION OF THE SYSTEM PHYSICIST BASICS. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(1), 64-74.
16. Bobokulova, M. (2024). THE ROLE OF NANOTECHNOLOGY IN MODERN PHYSICS. Development and innovations in science, 3(1), 145-153.
17. Bobokulova, M. X. (2023). STOMATOLOGIK MATERIALLARNING FIZIK-MEXANIK XOSSALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 223-228.
18. Xamroyevna, B. M. (2023). ORGANIZM TO 'QIMALARINING ZICHLIGINI ANIQLASH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 50-58.
19. Bobokulova, M. K. (2023). IMPORTANCE OF FIBER OPTIC DEVICES IN MEDICINE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 212-216.
20. Khamroyevna, M. B. (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOLOGICAL MEMBRANES, BIOPHYSICAL MECHANISMS OF MOVEMENT OF SUBSTANCES IN THE MEMBRANE. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 217-221.
21. Bobokulova, M. K. (2024). TOLALI OPTIKA ASBOBLARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 517-524.
22. Latipova, S. (2024). YUQORI SINIF GEOMETRIYA MAVZUSINI O'QITISHDA YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA METODLAR. SINKVEYN METODI, VENN DIAGRAMMASI METODLARI HAQIDA. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(3), 165-173.
23. Latipova, S. (2024, February). SAVOL-JAVOB METODI, BURCHAKLAR METODI, DEBAT

- (BAHS) METODLARI YORDAMIDA GEOMETRIYANI O'RGANISH. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 25-33).
24. Latipova, S., & Sharipova, M. (2024). KESIK PIRAMIDA MAVZUSIDA FOYDALANILADIGAN YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR. 6X6X6 METODI, BBB (BILARDIM, BILMOQCHIMAN, BILIB OLDIM) METODLARI HAQIDA. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(2), 40-48.
25. Latipova, S. (2024). 10-11 SINFLARDA STEREOOMETRIYA OQITISHNING ILMIY VA NAZARIY ASOSLARI. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(6), 27-35.
26. Latipova, S. (2024). HILFER HOSILASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 3(2), 122-130.
27. Latipova, S. (2024). HILFER MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALAR UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. Development and innovations in science, 3(2), 58-70.
28. Latipova, S. (2024). KESIK PIRAMIDA TUSHUNCHASI. KESIK PIRAMIDANING YON SIRTINI TOPIH FORMULALARI. Models and methods in modern science, 3(2), 58-71.
29. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In " Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
30. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2024). CAPUTO MA'NOSIDAGI KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO 'YICHA TO 'G 'RI MASALALAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 2(1), 375-382.
31. Latipova, S. S. (2023). SOLVING THE INVERSE PROBLEM OF FINDING THE SOURCE FUNCTION IN FRACTIONAL ORDER EQUATIONS. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 1(10), 13-23.
32. Tursunov, B. J., & Allanazarov, G. O. (2019). Perspektivnye tehnologii proizvodstva po uluchsheniyu kachestva benzina. Theory and practice of contemporary science, 3(45), 305-308.
33. Турсунов, Б. Ж., & Алланазаров, Г. О. (2019). Перспективные технологии производства по улучшению качества бензина. Теория и практика современной науки, (3 (45)), 305-308.
34. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Analysis of Concepts About the Effect of an Explosion in Solid Wednesday. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 296-304.
35. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). Methods of Control of Explosion Energy Distribution in Rocks. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(10), 108-117.
36. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGY FOR ENRICHMENT OF PURIFIC COPPER-ZINC ORE. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 288-293.
37. Tursunov, B. Z. (2023). ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS FOR OIL SLUDGE PROCESSING. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 280-287.
38. Jumaev, K., & Tursunov, B. (2022, December). Environmentally friendly technology for obtaining fuel briquettes from oil waste. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012005). IOP Publishing.

39. Sharipova, M., & Latipova, S. (2024). TAKRORIY GRUPPALASHLAR. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(3), 134-142.
40. Sharipova, M. (2024). TAQQOSLAMA TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING XOSSALARI. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(2), 68-78.
41. Sharipova, M. (2024). IKKI O'ZGARUVCHILI TENGSIZLIKLAR SISTEMASINI TAQQOSLAMALAR USULI BILAN YECHISH. Development and innovations in science, 3(2), 97-105.
42. Sharipova, M. (2024). BIRINCHI DARAJALI TAQQOSLAMALARNI YECHISH USULLARI. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(2), 60-69.
43. Latipova, S., & Sharipova, M. (2024). KESIK PIRAMIDA MAVZUSIDA FOYDALANILADIGAN YANGI PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR. 6X6X6 METODI, BBB (BILARDIM, BILMOQCHIMAN, BILIB OLDIM) METODLARI HAQIDA. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(2), 40-48.
44. Sharipova, M. (2024). IN THE FORM OF AN UNBOUNDED PARALLELEPIPED IN THE FIELD NONLOCAL BORDERLINE CONDITIONAL LINEAR THE REVERSE IS THE CASE. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 105-116.
45. Sharipova, M. (2024). FUNCTIONAL SPACES. IN SHORT REFLECTION PRINCIPLE. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 131-142.
46. Sharipova, M. (2024). A IS CORRECT OF THE INTEGRAL TO THE ECONOMY APPLICATIONS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 116-125.
47. Sharipova, M. (2024). ASYMMETRY AND KURTOSIS COEFFICIENTS. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 216-225.
48. Sharipova, M. (2024). TWO MULTIPLE OF THE INTEGRAL APPLICATIONS. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(1), 135-140.
49. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 360-365.
50. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 137-141.
51. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 135-138.
52. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. International journal of sciearchers, 2(2), 101-103.
53. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 245-248.
54. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). FUNKSIYALARNI KOEFFITSIENTLAR ORQALI FUNKSIYALARNI YAKINLASHTIRISH HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(34), 102-110.
55. Sharipova, M. (2023, December). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN STRAIGHT LINES AND PLANES IN SPACE. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 60-66).
56. Sharipova, M. (2023). FRACTIONAL DERIVATIVES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 106-113.

57. Sharipova, M. (2023). CORRECT PLACED AND CORRECT NOT PLACED ISSUES. *Models and methods in modern science*, 2(13), 115-121.
58. Sharipova, M. (2023). HEAT SPREAD EQUATION. *Инновационные исследования в науке*, 2(12), 50-56.
59. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). HIGH MATH SCORE AND INTERVAL ASSESSMENT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 420-424.
60. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). IN HIGHER MATHEMATICS, THE EXTREMUM OF A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 425-429.
61. Sharipova, M. P. (2024). ISSIQLIK TARQALISH TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 525-532.
62. Axmedova, Z. (2024). KOMPYUTER TESTLARINING MAQSADLARI, MAZMUNI VA TUZILISHI. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 3(3), 211-222.
63. Axmedova, Z. (2024). NODAVLAT O'QUV MARKAZLARI TIZIMI PLATFORMASI UCHUN MOBIL ILOVA YARATISH. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 3(6), 162-179.
64. Axmedova, Z. (2024). NODAVLAT O'QUV MARKAZLARI TIZIMI PLATFORMASI UCHUN MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASINI YARATISH. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(3), 83-93.
65. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). STRUCTURES OF SMALL DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 3(1), 97-107.
66. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). DATA BY COMBINING MAIL THROUGH TO SEND METHODS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 3(1), 198-207.
67. Akhmedova, Z., & Rahmatova, N. (2024). LMS (LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM) LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FEATURES. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(1), 85-94.
68. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). CREATION OF A DATABASE FOR THE SYSTEM PLATFORM OF NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 3(1), 106-116.
69. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). IPHONE OPERATIONAL IN THE SYSTEM MOBILE APPLICATIONS TO CREATE INTENDED PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENTS. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 3(1), 111-121.
70. Axmedova, Z. I. (2024). LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IMKONIYATLARI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 2(1), 509-516.
71. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASI BOSHQARISH TIZIMLARI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(34), 40-49.
72. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). CREATION AND PLACEMENT OF INTERACTIVE ELEMENTS. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(13), 120-128.
73. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). Programming Environments for Creating Mobile Applications on the Android Operating System. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 305-309.
74. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS, ELECTRONIC EDUCATION: TASKS AND OPPORTUNITIES. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of*

pedagogical sciences, 2(21), 171-177.

75. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) CAPABILITIES OF THE STATISTICAL DATABASE LANGUAGE. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 274-280.

76. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). SQL (STRUCTURED QUERY LANGUAGE) STATISTICAL PACKAGES OF CAPABILITIES. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(12), 781-787.

77. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA*, 1(6), 128-132.

78. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. *Development and innovations in science*, 2(11), 29-35.

79. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 201-205.

80. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157)*, 1(9), 201-205.

81. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(11), 368-372.

82. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. *International journal of scientific researchers*, 2(2).

83. Karimov, F. (2022). ANIQ INTEGRALNI TAQRIBIY HISOBLASH. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 14(14).

84. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(1), 95-104.

85. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 3(1), 117-124.

86. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 3(1), 108-115.

87. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 3(1), 122-130.

88. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 3(1), 208-215.

89. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(5), 269-273.

90. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(11).

91. Quvvatov, B. (2024). DIFFERENTSIAL TENGLAMALAR VA AMALIY ECHIMLAR ORQALI MAXSUS MODELLARNI QURISH. *Menejment va iqtisodiyotda ijtimoiy muammolarni hal qilish*, 3 (1), 108-115.

92. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g', Q. (2023). SUN'IY NERV TIZIMLARIDAN MODELLASHDA FOYDALANISH. Fan va texnologiyaning ko'p tarmoqli jurnali , 3 (5), 269-273.
93. Behruz Ulug'bek og', Q. (2023). TEXNOLOGIYA VA TIBBIYOT: DİNAMİK HAMKORLIK. Tadqiqot va ishlanmalar bo'yicha xalqaro multidisipliner jurnali , 10 (11).
94. Quvvatov, B. (2024). ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BOLGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. GAUSS KVADRATUR FORMULALARI. Models and methods in modern science, 3(2), 114-125.
95. Quvvatov, B. (2024). ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BOLGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. ORTOGONAL KOPHADLAR. Инновационные исследования в науке, 3(2), 47-59.
96. Quvvatov, B. (2024, February). ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BOLGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. REKURSIV TRAPETSIYALAR QOIDASI. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 41-51).

